

HYSTERISIS IN THE SOL-GEL TRANSFORMATIONS OF AGAR

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The phenomenon of hysteresis in the sol-gel transformations of agar sols have been studied under different conditions. A tentative theory based upon the assumption of orientation of the colloidal particles to form a structure has been presented.

It has been shown in a previous paper (Banerji and Ghosh, *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1939, 9, 148) that the change in the viscosity of agar sol with age is very slow. It has been concluded from these results that the aggregation tendency of agar particles and hence their orientation originating from a "loose crystallographic force" is a very slow process. From a study on the phenomenon of hysteresis on the sol-gel transformations of reversible sols like those of gelatin and soap (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1930, 194, 305) it has been pointed out that a difference in the melting and setting points of such gels or sols exists due to a slow process of orientation of the colloidal particles. In the present communication the phenomenon of hysteresis in the sol-gel transformations of agar sols has been studied under different conditions. The experimental details are the same as followed in the case of gelatin and soap sols (*cf.* Banerji and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*). The experimental results with agar sols are given below.

TABLE I

Melting		Setting		Melting		Setting	
Temp.	Time	Temp.	Time	Temp.	Time	Temp.	Time
Sol=1.5 g. in 100 c.c.				Sol=2.0 g. in 100 c.c.			
75°	1 min	27	11 min	80	1	27	8
70	1.5	30	19	75	1.5	30	15
65	3	35	45	70	2.5	35	40
60	15	—	—	65	21	—	—
55	30	—	—	60	30	—	—
Sol=2.5 g. in 100 c.c.				Sol=3.0 g. in 100 c.c.			
80	1.5	27	4	78	3.5	29	3
75	2.0	30	8	75	6	32	5
70	3.0	35	32	70	10	35	9
65	29	—	—			38	16
60	35	—	—	65	34	40	30
				60	40	—	—
Sol=4.0 g. in 100 c.c.							
78	4.5	30	2				
75	8.0	32	3.5				
70	18	35	6.5				
65	30	37	11				
		40	28				

If these results on the melting and setting points of agar gels and sols are plotted it is found that the differences in melting and setting points or the hysteresis in degree centigrades for 12 minutes of observation for different concentrations of agar sols are as follows:—

TABLE II

Conc. agar sol (%)	1.5	2	2.5	3	4
Hysteresis for 12 min.	33.5	38	38	31.5	35

The hysteresis in sol-gel transformations of agar first increases and then decreases, passes through a minimum and finally increases with the increasing concentrations of agar. This result is similar to that obtained previously with soap and gelatin sols. An explanation based on orientation of colloid particles and subsequent aggregation has been already developed.

Thus with an agar sol of 4% concentration, the difference between the melting and setting points for 12 minutes of observation is as high as 35° (*cf.* 4.5° with a 10% gelatin sol for the same period). It will be interesting to note that the viscosity change of an agar sol with time is also very slow in comparison to those observed in the case of a gelatin sol. It can therefore be concluded that in the case of reversible sols like soap, galatin and agar, the slower the increase in the viscosity of these sols with age, the greater is the degree of hysteresis in the sol-gel transformations. It has also been shown in the sol-gel transformations of other substances that hysteresis is considerably lowered by sowing a sol with already formed gel of the same concentration as this hastens the process of orientation. The results of similar experiments on agar sols have been shown below.

TABLE III

AGAR SOL CONC.—2%

Temp.	Melting Time.	Setting					
		Ordinary		Sown with gel		With stirring	
		Temp.	Time.	Temp.	Time.	Temp.	Time.
80	0.1 min.	27	8 min	27	5 min.	27	6 min.
75	1.5	30	15	30	11	30	13
70	2.5	35	40	35	20	35	30
65	21	—	—	—	—	—	—
60	35	—	—	—	—	—	—

If the time-temperature curve is plotted it is seen that the amount of hysteresis of 2% sol for twelve minutes diminishes from 39° to 34° on sowing and 35° on stirring.

It appears from these observations that the formation of a gel or separation of thick gelatinous precipitate in the cases of sol-gel transformation resembles to some extent the separation of solid from a supersaturated solution. When a sol is gradually cooled, more and more of aggregated molecules and colloid micelle appear and are in an oriented condition. The orientation is caused by a similar kind of force which causes crystallisation, but

the particles both of molecular and colloidal dimension are unable to form coarse aggregation because they are protected by a layer of water present on the surface of these particles. The experimental results on the gelation of agar sols show that previous inoculation of sols with gels of the same concentration and temperature hastens the process of gelation and hence this has a close resemblance to the separation of a solid from a supersaturated solution.

Bradford (*Biochem. J.*, 1920, 14, 91) points out that the formation of a gel by cooling a sol is a case of crystallisation from a supersaturated solution. Möller (*Kolloid Z.*, 1919, 67, 25) likewise believes gelatinisation to be a kind of crystallisation in which a lattice is formed that entrains some liquid within it, and Von Weimern (*Z. Chem. Ind. Koll.*, 1912, 11, 239) concludes from his investigations that a jelly is a sponge composed of highly disposed crystallised granules soaked in a dispersive medium. It may be of interest to recall here that the process of sol-gel transformation is a continuous process and there is no evidence to show that aggregation of colloid particles or of heavy molecules present in the gelatin, soap or agar sol, is suddenly rapid when a gel separates out. Thus Walpole (*Kolloid Z.*, 1913, 13, 241) showed that the refractive index changed slowly but continuously as a gelatin sol was allowed to gelate. Also, it has been observed here that when 1% agar sol is allowed to gelatinise slowly at a temperature of 29.5°, the change in the extinction coefficient as observed with a Nutting's Spectrophotometer in the region, 6000 Å is extremely slow and is practically constant (Table IV).

TABLE IV

Agar sol conc. = 1% Temp. = 29.5°

Condition	Time	Extnc. coeff.
Sol.	5 min.	0.12
"	20	0.12
"	35	0.12
Gel.	50	0.12

From these results it is concluded that there is practically no change in the number, size or structure of colloid particles during the course of the setting of agar sol because the amount of light transmitted does not differ.

It is well known that there exists a considerable disagreement as to the structure and phase of a gel system. Katz (*Koll.-Chem. Beih.*, 1917, 9, 1) discusses a gel as a homogeneous phase whilst several investigators consider a gel as made up of two phases. Ultramicroscopic study beginning with the work of Zsigmondy (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1911, 71, 358) has shown that many gels are apparently without structure and in some cases, a structure is seen where fibrils join and intersect as long straight threads. McBain and co-workers (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1921, 98, A, 395) report such structure in the case of soap gels, whilst Barret (*Biochem. J.*, 1920, 14, 198) has shown the existence of fibrils in the case of fibrinogen.

It has already been pointed out that the process of the separation of gel from a sol is not a sudden process and gelation of sols like agar, gelatin or soap is continuous. It has also been shown that there is an orientation of colloid particles in the sol state and the sols may show a distinct rigidity. This orientation of colloid particles, which imparts a rigidity rapidly increases with the lowering of temperature and with time.

It is, therefore, suggested that at the moment when a gel is formed from a sol, the orientation of colloidal micelle has reached the highest value to attain the rigidity which characterises a solid body from the condition of a liquid. When, therefore, the 1% sol of agar is kept at a temperature of 30°, the number of colloidal micellae is not increasing with increasing time but they are gradually arranging themselves to an oriented form. This orientation is a very slow process because of the slow diffusion of the dispersed particles. When finally sufficient orientation has been reached the sol appears as a gel, where the aggregation of the dispersed agar particles is not much different from that in the sol condition. The coarsening is stopped as has already been pointed out, by the hydration of the colloidal micelle. When however the gel is kept for a sufficiently long time, the colloid particles gradually lose the affinity for water, get dehydrated and aggregation occurs and finally the phenomenon of syneresis is observable. It is well known that substances lose their adsorptive capacity with time. It is therefore suggested that in those cases where an evidence of the structure of a gel has been obtained from ultramicroscopic observations, the colloid particles have lost some of the protecting layer of water and their aggregation has set in.

It may be of interest to mention here that Schalek and Szegvary (*Kolloid, Z.*, 1923, 33, 326) studied the effect of shaking on the concentrated and aged sols of ferric hydroxide. These sols set to a gel on addition of an electrolyte of suitable concentration, the gels on shaking become less viscous and mobile again and the sols thus formed gelate again, the whole process being capable of repetition. They have measured the viscosity change during gelation and have followed the process of the changes by an ultramicroscope. They show that in the course of gelation the particles do not meet each other. Their results greatly support the views developed here for the process of gelation from a sol.

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